

Original Research

Labour Market Participation: How Do Men and Women Compare in South Africa?

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Abstract

Throughout history, industries have evolved, from the invention of hand axes by our ancient ancestors to the Internet of Things, which has profoundly influenced every aspect of life. Despite these advancements, women still encounter numerous obstacles in making ends meet. The crux of this study is to highlight key areas where meaningful gender equality can be achieved. This consists of, among other things, working hours, access to social protection, and occupational segregation. We find substantial gender disparities in the labour force, both in terms of the number and quality of jobs. Although there are more women in the working-age population than men, men's participation in the labour force significantly surpasses that of women. Consequently, a higher proportion of men are in paid employment compared to women. In terms of employment conditions, we find that gender gaps have reduced, indicating that men and women now work under similar terms and conditions compared to a decade ago. Similarly, we find that gender disparities in political representation have somewhat narrowed in the last decade. Given the challenges that women face in navigating the labour market, a crucial intervention should focus on enhancing the employability of women. Employability refers to the skills and attributes that make individuals more appealing to employers and empower them to successfully navigate the job market and workplace. Other interventions should aim to promote a work-family balance for women by providing them with access to adequate social protection measures, considering that the majority of unpaid family care responsibilities fall on women.

Keywords: Economic empowerment, Gender differences, Labour force.

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Introduction

In an ideal world, women and men would be different but equal. However, history, dominant belief systems and cultural norms have created an uneven playing field for women. What has become clear is that equality of opportunities doesn't always lead to equal economic outcomes. There remains a substantial number of underutilised and misallocated skills and talents by women worldwide. The lack of access to quality education for women hinders their ability to develop the human and social capital necessary for economic participation (Duflo, 2012). Those with access to quality education encounter other social challenges (e.g., motherhood) in the later years of their careers which limits the amount of time they can dedicate to paid work. This not only influences their career trajectory but also creates disparities in remuneration relative to their male counterparts (Blau & Kahn, 2003). The study of gender inequality has gained considerable attention in the past three decades given the crucial role played by women in macroeconomic and financial stability. When women and children are part of the economic agenda, the government can distribute and utilise productive resources in the most efficient and economical manner. Joshi et al., (2007) posit that women's contributions to the economy also extend to building stable and resilient societies, essential for maintaining law and order.

Over the past few decades, countries have sought to eliminate barriers to women's economic participation, particularly through legal reform. For instance, in Indonesia, several laws were implemented which protect women from sexual harassment in the workplace (Anukriti et al., 2023). Meanwhile, the Mongolian government enacted laws that guarantee equal remuneration for work of equal value. More recently in Sub-Saharan Africa, the Republic of Congo and Côte d'Ivoire enacted legislation protecting women from various forms of domestic violence. Although considerable progress has been made to date, women still experience barriers to social and economic participation. For example, the majority of women in the Middle East and North Africa experience restrictions on the freedom of movement, including the ability to choose where to live in the same manner as a man. To this end, in 19 economies around the world, a woman cannot get a job in the same way as a man. As if that wasn't enough, there exist several restrictive laws and regulations affecting a woman's ability to earn equal pay for work of equal value, and her ability to work in the same sectors and industries as men globally.

The Covid19 pandemic has likewise reversed years of economic progress in reducing gender inequality given its disproportionate impact on women and children. There remain some considerable disparities in gender gaps at the regional level. The most recent Africa Gender Report (2019) revealed that African countries score between 24% and 80% in the gender index² with an average score of 48% (United Nations, 2020). Due to the lack of access to quality education and healthcare, women often find themselves in informal, low-paying jobs that are not protected by labour laws. This is further exacerbated by conventional societal expectations for women to engage in unpaid domestic work and childcare which are often not recognised as formal contributions to society (Manning & Farzad, 2010). This becomes more evident during the marriage dissolution process. Another major driver of gender inequality is the lack of access to productive assets such

² A score between 0 and 1 implies that there is gender inequality in favour of men.

as land which often serves as collateral to access credit. Without adequate collateral to access funding, women become strangled in poverty and subsistence farming. The African Development Bank (2020; 14) notes that “in both the private and public sectors, senior decision-making remains substantially in the hands of men”. However, in parliaments that are dominated by women, gender-balanced programs tend to form the crux of policymaking.

It becomes the primary goal of this study to measure gender disparities in the South African labour force. The majority of studies that measure gender disparities have been conducted at the regional and global level and as such, country-specific studies remain scant. Although Nishimwe-Niyimbanira and Sabela (2019) conducted a similar study in the context of South Africa, the disproportionate effect of the COVID-19 pandemic was not observed, a gap this study aims to address. Measuring gender disparities in economic participation is crucial to informed policymaking. Moreover, the effectiveness of several policies that are aimed at addressing past imbalances through equality of opportunity remains under scrutiny. As such, this study will play a crucial role in determining whether the South African government’s effort in promoting economic empowerment has benefited all segments of society without leaving others behind. The rest of the study will be organised as follows: the first section of the study details the introduction and background to the research topic and ultimately outlines the objective and contribution of the study to the existing body of literature. The second section of the study will provide an empirical assessment of the literature on the role of women in the economy as well as various elements of women's economic participation. The third segment of the study will detail the empirical strategy while the fourth segment of the study will provide a summary of findings and discussions. The last section of the study will detail the conclusion, research limitations and recommendations.

Conceptual framework and literature review

Women’s economic empowerment can be defined as the process of ensuring that women have equal access to economic opportunities such as quality education and healthcare, social protection, paid employment and venture capital (Johnson, 2005). Salem et al., (2018) note that women’s economic empowerment is about ensuring that women benefit in the same manner as their male counterparts in economic opportunities given that equality of opportunity does not necessarily translate to equal economic outcomes. Various elements shape the concept of women’s economic empowerment such as voice, agency and economic participation. For completeness, voice and agency refer to the ability of women to make unlimited decisions about their individual development, to have complete control and ownership of productive assets and resources as well as to participate meaningfully and equally in decision-making in all spheres of management (Miedema, 2018).

Gender equality is not only a human right, but also a pre-condition for economic development. Several studies (e.g., Kowalewska & Vitali, 2021) have also established that gender equality and economic growth are jointly determined, in that, gender equality contributes positively to economic growth while economic growth, in turn, augments higher levels of gender equality. Increasing gender equality is associated with several benefits in various areas of policy-making including education, pay gap, labour force

participation, and political representation. Albanesi (2012) posits that improving gender equality through access to quality education has the potential to reduce the child and infant mortality rate while increasing the life expectancy rate through better family and child health.

Figure 1. Elements of women's economic empowerment
Source: Amore et al., (2014)

Several studies documenting gender disparities in economic participation are discussed below. A study by Daly (2007) found that equality and fairness in the labour market are associated with reductions in the gender employment gap and subsequently higher levels of national output, at least in the Euro area. A more recent study by Rossi and Sierminska (2014) showed that policies aimed at reducing the gender pay gap encourage women to contribute a larger fraction of their wages to savings. A study by Bettio et al., (2012) examined the impact of the sovereign debt crisis on women and men in Europe. The study revealed that the sovereign debt crisis and subsequent economic meltdown levelled the gender gaps in poverty, remuneration and employment. The study further revealed that due to the high level of labour market segregation, men experienced more retrenchments relative to their female counterparts. For completeness, there is an over-representation of women in public sector jobs than in previously male-dominated sectors such as manufacturing and construction where the bulk of retrenchments occur during crisis. The study concluded that recent proposals to implement austerity measures to curb rising government debt will have a disastrous impact on civil servants which comprise mainly of women.

Raney et al., (2011) investigated the contribution of women in agriculture and the rural economy. The study argues that women often face constraints that limit their productivity. The study further revealed that the contribution of women in agriculture is marked by differences in ethnic group, social class, age and activity. Surveys on time use indicate that weeding and harvesting were predominantly female activities. Overall, the study finds that the labour burden of rural women exceeds that of men, particularly because women spend the bulk of their time in unpaid household activities such as preparing food, and fetching water and fuel, all of which cannot be measured. Research by the

Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (2018) explored some of the drivers of the digital gender divide in G20 economies such as difficulties in access, affordability, socio-cultural norms, inherent biases and a lack of quality education. The study argued that low levels of educational enrolment by females in those subjects that would enable them to perform better in a digital world, coupled with the limited access to and use of digital devices and platforms, is indicative of a widening gender gap more especially in digital transformation.

A study by Bertrand et al., (2010) examined the dynamics of the gender gaps among young professionals in the corporate and financial sectors. The sample population consisted of MBA graduates from a top business school in the United States. The study revealed that male and female MBA graduates are remunerated equally during the early years of completing their MBA studies. However, this pattern changes over time owing to various factors including prior training, career interruptions and differences in hours dedicated to work. The study argues that women often deal with motherhood responsibilities during the later years of their careers which limits the number of hours they can dedicate to work and hence the shortfall in remuneration. Shaw & Mariano (2021) argued that if women were remunerated in the same manner as their male counterparts for the same value of work, taking into account demographic factors such as age, level of schooling, number of hours worked and location, the poverty rate for working women and their families would be reduced by approximately 40% in the United States. Yoong, Rabinovich and Diepeveen (2012) conducted a systematic review of the impact of resource transfers on women compared to men. The key finding of the study was that resource transfers to women do not only improve the well-being of the recipients but are also passed on to their children in the form of investments in child healthcare and education.

A study by Kim et al., (2016) considered a model for gender inequality and economic growth by linking the amount of time women allocate towards market production, child-rearing, household responsibilities and the rate of economic growth. Notably, the study made use of micro-level data from Asian economies. The findings revealed that aggregate income would increase by nearly 10.5% on average while the corresponding GDP per capita would increase by nearly 50% on average if gender inequality was completely addressed in Asian economies. Rubiano-Matulevich & Viollaz (2019) investigated gender disparities in the allocation of time between remunerative work and unpaid care work. The study focused on 19 countries in different regions and across different income levels. The findings revealed that women tend to allocate more time to unpaid domestic work while men channel the bulk of their time into remunerative work. The findings further revealed that men typically benefit from marriage and parenthood while women, on the other hand, are penalised on a variety of measures including participation in the labour force as a result of marriage and parenthood.

A more recent study by Ferrant & Thim (2019) employed time-use surveys to measure the level of women's economic empowerment in South Africa, Peru, Bangladesh and Ethiopia. The findings revealed that unpaid work contributes nearly 14% to GDP in South Africa and 33% to China. The study further argued that the extent to which education leads to a decline in the time allocated for unpaid work largely depends on the level of educational attainment. For instance, tertiary education significantly affects the time

allocated to unpaid work while primary education has little to no impact on the time allocated to unpaid work.

Empirical strategy

This section outlines the data collection and analysis process. This includes the type and frequency of data as well as the estimation technique. The study made use of quarterly time series data spanning from the first quarter of 2008 to the fourth quarter of 2023. The data was sourced from the Quarterly Labour Force Survey (QLFS) conducted by Statistics South Africa. The QLFS is a household-based sample survey which gathers data on people who are 15 years of age and older, who are actively engaged in the labour market. The survey provides key statistics on the official employment rate and unemployment statistics in South Africa. This study employed quantitative research methods, particularly descriptive analysis. The choice of method was largely influenced by the characteristics of the data. Descriptive analysis is a useful tool for organising data and making inferences on the relationship between variables in a sample (Naape, 2023).

Descriptive analysis is characterized by several measures of discrepancy, central tendency, frequency and position (Ali & Bhaskar, 2016). Measures of central tendency include the median, mode and mean while measures of frequency consist of the percentage and frequency. Measures of discrepancy, on the other hand, comprise the standard deviation, range, quartile and coefficient of variation. Kaur et al., (2018) note that descriptive analysis has become a crucial part of statistical analysis and should thus be conducted prior to inferential and regression analysis. Loeb et al., (2017; 3) argue that “whether the goal is to identify and describe trends and variation in populations, create new measures of key phenomena, or simply describe samples in studies aimed at identifying causal effects, descriptive analyses are part of almost every empirical paper and report”. Lans and Van Der Voordt (2002) add that a key advantage of using descriptive analysis lies in its high degree of neutrality and objectivity.

Findings and discussions

This section provides a summary of findings and discussions. The findings presented are based on the strict definition of employment. Table 1 below illustrates gender gaps in the labour force between 2014 and 2023. Although there are higher rates of women in the working-age population relative to their male counterparts, the labour force participation of males outpaces that of women by a great degree.

Table 1. Labour force characteristics by sex (2014 Q2-2023 Q2)

	2014		2018		2019		2023		2014	2018	2019	2023
	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	Gender Gaps			
Working age (15-64 yrs.)	49.2	50.8	49.5	50.5	49.5	50.5	49.6	50.4	-1.6	-1.1	-1.0	-0.8
Labour Force	63.9	50.9	65.5	52.9	66.2	53.5	64.9	54.3	13.0	12.6	12.7	10.6
Employed	76.2	72.5	74.7	70.5	72.9	68.7	70.0	64.3	3.8	4.2	4.2	5.7
Formal sector (Non-agricultural)	73.9	67.8	71.0	67.5	70.0	66.6	69.3	69.4	6.1	3.5	3.4	-0.1

Informal sector (Non-agricultural)	17.2	13.9	19.5	14.6	20.5	16.3	21.2	15.1	3.3	4.9	4.2	6.1
Agriculture	5.5	3.1	6.2	3.9	6.5	3.5	6.7	3.9	2.3	2.3	3.0	2.8
Private households	3.4	15.1	3.3	14.0	3.0	13.7	2.8	11.6	-11.8	-10.7	-10.6	-8.8
Unemployed	23.8	27.5	25.3	29.5	27.1	31.3	30.0	35.7	-3.7	-4.2	-4.2	-5.7
Not economically active	36.1	49.1	34.5	47.1	33.8	46.5	35.1	45.7	-12.9	-12.6	-12.7	-10.7
Discouraged work-seekers	6.5	7.1	6.8	8.3	6.5	7.8	7.5	8.1	-0.6	-1.5	-1.3	-0.5
Other (not economically active)	29.6	41.9	27.7	38.7	27.3	38.7	27.5	37.7	-12.3	-11.0	-11.4	-10.1

Source: QLFS 2008-2023 (Statistics SA); Own Calculations

In 2014, the gender gap in labour force participation stood at 13% although it decreased slightly to 12.6% in 2018. While the share of men in the labour force declined from 66.2% to 64.9% during the COVID-19 period, the share of women in the labour force increased from 53.5% to 54.3% during the same period. Of the total men in the labour force, 76.2% of males were employed in 2014 compared to 72.5% of females. This brought the gender gap in employment to 3.8% in 2014 which increased further to 4.2% in 2018. Mathebula & Naape (2023) established that the COVID-19 pandemic had a disproportionate effect on women and children and this can be seen in the changes in employment rates among men and women. For instance, the share of employed males declined from 72.9% to 70% (-2.9%) during the covid19 period while the share of employed females decreased from 68.7% to 64.3% (-4.4%) during the same period. On the upside, the share of women occupying jobs in the formal sector increased significantly during the COVID-19 pandemic compared to their male counterparts. This, to some extent, implies that the working conditions of females in the labour force are slightly improving in South Africa given that jobs in the formal sector are usually protected by labour laws. Nevertheless, women still account for the majority of the “not economically active” population in South Africa. The gender gap in this category has however slightly decreased from 12.9% in 2014 to 10.7% in 2023. Table 2 illustrates gender gaps in employment by economic sector.

Table 2. Employed by sex and economic sector (2014 Q2-2023 Q2)

	2014		2018		2019		2023		2014	2018	2019	2023
	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	Gender Gaps			
Agriculture	5.5	3.1	6.2	3.9	6.5	3.5	6.7	3.9	2.3	2.3	3.0	2.8
Mining	4.1	1.1	4.1	0.8	3.6	0.7	4.1	1.0	2.9	3.3	2.9	3.1
Manufacturing	13.9	8.6	12.7	8.2	13.2	8.1	11.5	7.0	5.3	4.5	5.1	4.5
Utilities	1.1	0.4	1.2	0.7	1.1	0.7	1.0	0.5	0.7	0.6	0.4	0.5
Construction	12.5	1.9	14.4	2.2	13.2	2.1	12.5	2.1	10.6	12.2	11.2	10.4
Trade	19.8	22.6	18.4	21.5	19.7	22.7	19.8	21.6	-2.8	-3.2	-3.1	-1.8
Transport	9.1	2.6	8.9	2.8	8.8	2.4	8.5	2.9	6.5	6.0	6.4	5.5
Finance	13.9	12.6	15.1	14.3	16.1	14.2	16.0	15.8	1.2	0.8	1.9	0.2

	2014		2018		2019		2023		2014	2018	2019	2023
	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	Gender Gaps			
Community and social services	16.7	31.9	15.8	31.5	14.7	31.8	17.1	33.5	-15.2	-15.7	-17.1	-16.4
Private households	3.4	15.1	3.3	14.0	3.0	13.7	2.8	11.6	-11.8	-10.7	-10.6	-8.8
Other	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	-0.1	0.0	0.0

Source: QLFS 2008-2023 (Statistics SA); Own Calculations

The majority of women occupy positions in the trade, private households, community and social services sectors. Patterns in historically male-dominated sectors haven't changed much in the last decade nor during the COVID-19 pandemic. The majority of men occupy positions in the mining, construction, manufacturing, finance and transport sectors. The gender gaps are wider in the construction and transport sectors. Table 3 summarises gender gaps in employment by occupation. The findings indicate that women are largely concentrated in clerical, elementary and sales work. Also, compared to their male counterparts, women make a significant share of domestic work in South Africa although the gender gap in domestic work has slightly decreased in the last decade. Men on the other hand occupy plant and machine work, managerial, craft and related trade positions. Significant gender imbalances can be observed in domestic work, technicians, plant and machine operators, craft and related trade as well as clerical work. It is sufficient to note that patterns in managerial positions have slightly changed post-covid19 although the share of women in managerial positions falls short of their male counterparts. Nishimwe-Niymanira & Sabela (2019) argue that occupation segregation augments contribute significantly to gender gaps, both in terms of number and the quality of jobs.

Table 3. Employed by sex and occupation (2014 Q2-2023 Q2)

	2014		2018		2019		2023		2014	2018	2019	2023
	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	Gender Gaps			
Manager	10.4	6.1	10.6	6.3	11.5	6.6	8.4	5.3	4.3	4.3	5.0	3.2
Professional	6.2	6.0	4.9	6.0	4.3	6.2	7.2	8.4	0.2	-1.1	-1.8	-1.2
Technician	8.3	13.4	7.1	11.2	7.3	10.7	7.4	11.1	-5.0	-4.1	-3.4	-3.7
Clerk	5.8	17.6	5.1	17.3	5.2	17.2	6.6	17.5	-11.8	-12.2	-12.0	-11.0
Sales and services	13.8	16.7	15.0	17.7	15.3	18.0	15.6	19.4	-2.9	-2.8	-2.8	-3.8
Skilled agriculture	0.5	0.3	0.5	0.2	0.5	0.1	0.5	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.3
Craft and related trade	18.2	3.0	19.5	3.1	18.9	3.2	15.6	2.8	15.3	16.4	15.7	12.8
Plant and machine operator	13.0	2.4	12.9	2.6	13.2	2.4	12.2	1.9	10.6	10.3	10.8	10.3
Elementary	23.2	19.8	24.1	22.0	23.2	22.3	26.0	22.3	3.4	2.0	1.0	3.6
Domestic worker	0.5	14.8	0.3	13.5	0.4	13.4	0.5	11.1	-14.3	-13.2	-12.9	-10.5
Other	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0

Source: QLFS 2008-2023 (Statistics SA); Own Calculations

Table 4 indicates gender gaps in the status of employment between 2014 and 2023. The period between 2014 and 2023 has witnessed an increase in the number of women with own-account worker status. Also, the number of men with employer status continues to outweigh the number of women with employer status. The gender gap in employer

status stood at 4.9% in 2014 before increasing slightly to 5.3% in 2019. In contrast, the share of women with employee status continues to outweigh that of their male counterparts, averaging 5.25% during the period under consideration.

Table 4. Employed by sex and status in employment (2014Q2-2023 Q2)

	2014		2018		2019		2023		2014	2018	2019	2023
	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	Gender Gaps			
Employee	84.2	88.6	82.5	88.4	81.4	86.7	81.2	86.6	-4.4	-5.9	-5.3	-5.4
Employer	7.4	2.5	7.0	2.1	7.8	2.6	7.5	3.3	4.9	4.9	5.3	4.2
Own-account worker	8.1	8.3	10.1	8.8	10.4	9.8	10.8	9.4	-0.2	1.2	0.7	1.4
Unpaid household member	0.3	0.6	0.4	0.7	0.4	1.0	0.5	0.7	-0.3	-0.3	-0.6	-0.2

Source: QLFS 2008-2023 (Statistics SA); Own Calculations

Table 5 summarises findings on gender gaps by usual hours of work. The findings reveal that the predominant working hours among men and women is 40 hours or more. Although the incidence of women working between 40-45 hours per week has grown in the last decade compared to their male counterparts, the incidence of men working more than 45 hours per week has likewise outpaced that of their female counterparts in the last decade and by a large margin. The gender gap in working 40-45 hours per week widened from 10.4% in 2014 to 12.3% in 2023.

Table 5. Employed by sex and usual hours of work (2014 Q2-2023 Q2)

	2014		2018		2019		2023		2014	2018	2019	2023
	M	W	M	W	M	W	M	W	Gender Gaps			
Working less than 15 hours per week	1.5	3.2	1.5	2.8	1.4	3.0	2.3	3.7	-1.7	-1.3	-1.6	-1.4
Working 15-29 hours per week	4.0	9.0	4.3	9.7	4.5	10.2	5.0	9.9	-5.0	-5.4	-5.6	-4.9
Working 30-39 hours per week	4.9	9.6	4.9	9.1	4.7	9.6	5.7	9.4	-4.7	-4.2	-4.9	-3.7
Working 40-45 hours per week	56.3	55.3	55.9	56.6	54.4	54.8	54.9	57.3	1.0	-0.7	-0.4	-2.4
Working more than 45 hours per week	33.3	22.8	33.4	21.7	35.0	22.5	32.1	19.7	10.4	11.7	12.5	12.3

Source: QLFS 2008-2023 (Statistics SA); Own Calculations

Table 6 illustrates gender gaps in the duration of employment. Although the majority of men and women are in permanent employment, the gap between men and women in permanent employment has somewhat narrowed between 2014 and 2019. There are, however, more women than men in limited-duration employment and this gap has somewhat increased from 1.9% in 2014 to 3.6% in 2023. A slightly equal share of men and women occupy jobs with an unspecified duration.

Table 6. duration of employment by sex (2014 Q2-2023 Q2)

	2014		2018		2019		2023		2014	2018	2019	2023
	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	Gender Gaps			
Limited duration	14.5	16.5	11.8	15.3	11.9	15.2	14.2	17.8	-1.9	-3.5	-3.3	-3.6
Permanent nature	64.7	59.9	62.1	59.3	62.7	60.1	61.0	57.9	4.8	2.8	2.6	3.0
Unspecified duration	20.8	23.6	26.1	25.4	25.4	24.7	24.8	24.3	-2.8	0.7	0.7	0.6

Source: QLFS 2008-2023 (Statistics SA); Own Calculations

Table 7 indicates gender gaps in conditions of employment. Nearly 52% of men employed were covered by pension arrangements compared to only 45% of women employed. This brought the gender gap in pension savings arrangements to 7.4% in 2014. On the upside, this trend has since declined, bringing the gender gap in pension savings to only 2.7% by 2023. A similar trend can be observed in the gap between men and women entitled to paid leave and paid sick leave. Although the majority of men employed were entitled to paid leave and paid sick leave relative to their female counterparts a decade ago, this gap stood at 0.4% and 0.7% for paid leave and paid sick leave, respectively, in 2023. In contrast, the number of employed women entitled to maternity leave far outpaced that of men entitled to paternity leave and this gap has increased from 1.5% in 2014 to 6% in 2023.

Table 7. Condition of employment by sex (2014 Q2-2023 Q2)

	2014		2018		2019		2023		2014	2018	2019	2023
	M	F	M	F	M	F	M	F	Gender Gaps			
Pension/retirement fund contribution												
Yes	52.0	44.6	50.4	45.4	50.5	45.7	45.4	42.8	7.4	5.0	4.7	2.7
No	45.9	53.5	47.7	53.1	47.0	52.5	51.1	54.4	-7.6	-5.4	-5.5	-3.4
Don't know	2.1	1.9	1.9	1.5	2.5	1.8	3.5	2.8	0.2	0.3	0.8	0.7
Entitled to any paid leave												
Yes	66.5	61.8	67.3	64.6	67.9	65.3	66.2	65.7	4.7	2.7	2.6	0.4
No	32.1	36.9	31.8	34.5	30.8	33.9	32.0	32.9	-4.8	-2.7	-3.1	-0.9
Don't know	1.4	1.3	1.0	0.9	1.3	0.8	1.9	1.4	0.1	0.1	0.5	0.4
Entitled to paid sick leave												
Yes	70.5	66.2	71.3	68.9	72.0	69.8	72.4	71.7	4.3	2.4	2.2	0.7
No	29.5	33.8	28.7	31.1	28.0	30.2	25.8	26.9	-4.3	-2.4	-2.2	-1.2
Don't know							1.9	1.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.5
Entitled to maternity/paternity leave												
Yes	51.6	53.1	55.7	58.0	55.6	59.1	51.8	57.8	-1.5	-2.3	-3.6	-6.0
No	48.4	46.9	44.3	42.0	44.4	40.9	44.7	39.9	1.5	2.3	3.6	4.8
Don't know							3.6	2.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.3
UIF contribution												
Yes	64.6	54.8	63.3	56.7	63.9	55.1	64.3	60.3	9.8	6.6	8.8	4.0
No	33.4	43.2	35.2	41.8	32.9	40.8	33.1	37.0	-9.8	-6.6	-7.9	-3.9
Don't know	2.0	2.0	1.5	1.5	2.1	2.1	2.6	2.7	0.0	0.0	0.0	-0.1
Medical aid benefits												
Yes	32.5	29.7	30.6	28.6	30.0	28.7	29.2	29.8	2.8	2.0	1.4	-0.6
No	66.3	69.2	68.5	70.7	67.7	68.3	68.9	68.5	-2.9	-2.2	-0.6	0.4
Don't know	1.2	1.2	0.9	0.8	1.1	1.1	1.9	1.7	0.1	0.2	0.0	0.2

Source: QLFS 2008-2023 (Statistics SA); Own Calculations

Observations from Table 7 also indicate that a larger proportion of employed men are covered by UIF contribution arrangements compared to their female counterparts although this gap has somewhat decreased from 9.8% in 2014 to 4% in 2023. Similarly, there has been a change in the pattern of men and women with access to medical aid

benefits over the last decade. The share of employed women with access to medical aid benefits has somewhat surpassed that of their male counterparts although the majority of employed men and women are still without access to medical aid benefits. Table 8 illustrates gender gaps in political representation. This is measured by the proportion of seats held by women in the national parliament.

Table 8. Political representation

Year	M	F	Gender Gap
2014	58.5	41.5	17.0
2018	57.3	42.7	14.5
2019	53.7	46.3	7.3
2022	53.5	46.5	7.0

Source: World Development Indicators (World Bank); Own Calculations

Gender disparities in political representation have somewhat narrowed in the last decade. Nearly 47% of women occupy seats in the national parliament compared to 41.5% a decade ago. This has narrowed the gender gap from 17% in 2014 to 7% in 2022. Devlin & Elgie (2008) argued that involving women in the decision-making process in national government creates a platform for women to challenge both the power structures and relations that undermine the consideration of women's needs and interest in policy-making.

Conclusion and recommendations

The core of this study was to highlight key areas where meaningful gender equality can be achieved. This consisted of, among other things, working hours, access to social protection, and occupational segregation. The study employed quarterly time series data sourced from Statistics South Africa's flagship report "Quarterly Labour Force Survey". The data was scrutinized using descriptive analysis. We find substantial gender disparities in the labour force, both in terms of the number and quality of jobs. The findings reveal that although there are higher rates of women in the working-age population relative to their male counterparts, the labour force participation of males outpaces that of women by a great degree. This has seemingly translated into a larger proportion of men in paid employment than their female counterparts, particularly in critical economic sectors such as manufacturing, mining, construction and transport services.

With regard to conditions of employment, such as pension fund contributions, provisions for paid leave, UIF contributions and medical aid benefits, we find that gender gaps have somewhat narrowed in the last decade, implying that both men and women work under slightly the same terms and conditions of employment today, compared to a decade ago. Lastly, we find that gender disparities in political representation have somewhat narrowed in the last decade, indicating that more women are involved in the decision-making process at the national government level. Considering the challenges that women face in navigating the labour market, a crucial intervention should focus on enhancing the employability of women. Employability refers to the skills and attributes that make individuals more appealing to employers and empower them to successfully navigate the job market and workplace. Other interventions should aim to promote a

work-family balance for women by providing them with access to adequate social protection measures, considering that the majority of unpaid family care responsibilities fall on women.

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